

D4.3

Data collection template for cost benefit analysis: Accompanying reading guide to the D4.3 Excel file

Control Union Certifications Germany GmbH (CU)

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AUTHORS (Organisation)	Karolina Niemenoja (Control Union Certifications Germany GmbH)
REVIEWERS	Iris Vural Gursel, Heleen Ballemans (WFBR), Lusine Aramyan (WEcR)
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ABBREVIATIONS

BC	Better Cotton
CU	Control Union Certifications Germany GmbH
WEcR	Wageningen Economic Research
CBA	Cost Benefit Analysis
GRS	Global Recycled Standard
FSC	Forest Stewardship Council

Executive Summary

The output of Task 4.3 is an Excel file *D4.3_Data collection template for cost benefit analysis*, as well as the accompanying reading guide (this document). The goal of this template is to facilitate collection of data on biobased value chains for carrying out cost benefit analysis (CBA) of adoption of sustainability certification schemes and labels. The template was developed following the CBA methodology and data needs identified in Task 4.1 and described in Deliverable D4.1.

In this project, this template is tested for the assessment of three biobased value chains that were selected. This selection was done part of Task 4.2 and described in Deliverable D4.2. These three biobased value chains belong to the chemical (ethanol from sugarcane), textile (cotton), and construction (wood) sectors, respectively. The template for conducting a cost benefit analysis of biobased value chains has been further developed by implementing the feedback from its testing in these selected value chains. The first value chain for which the template was filled was the sugarcane to ethanol value chain in Brazil belonging to the chemical sector, followed by the cotton and wood value chains. This testing provides applicability of the template for the specific value chain and scheme chosen, the geographical area under consideration, as well as considering different value chain actors.

This reading guide serves as a document further explaining the nature of data to be collected, as well as how the template can be filled with the collected data. Guiding documents, which were developed as part of this task to facilitate the data collection process, are also included in the Annex of this reading guide. These concern data collection questionnaires tailored to three sectors: chemical, textile and construction; Annex 1 includes an example questionnaire used in the construction sector. The Annex 2 provides the communication document and presentation prepared for engaging with potential companies to collect data.

Explanation of the testing of this template on these three biobased value chains and the guiding documents developed for the collection of data, can be utilized in tailoring them to the needs of the assessor for collection of data for CBA of other value chains and certifications combinations beyond the SUSTCERT4BIOBASED project.

1. Introduction

The objective of this task is the development of a data collection template and guiding documents to facilitate collection of data on biobased value chains for carrying out cost benefit analysis (CBA) of adoption of sustainability certification schemes and labels. This template is being used and tested in the SUSTCERT4BIOBASED project for the three selected biobased value chains representing the chemicals, textile, and construction sectors. The value chains considered for these sectors are the production of ethanol from sugarcane, cotton and wood, respectively. The template has been developed following the methodology and the data needs identified in Task 4.1 and adapted to be applicable for different biobased value chains and certification schemes, different geographical areas, as well as the different value chain actors. The data collection template is provided as an Excel file deliverable titled *D4.3_Data collection template for cost benefit analysis*. This reading guide has been provided alongside this document, which has the aim of explaining the data collection approach as well as describing how the Excel template can be filled.

Data for the Excel template for the three biobased value chains was gathered by engaging with relevant stakeholders through different channels. This includes data collection questionnaires and communication documents for inviting stakeholders. Examples of these guiding documents are provided in the Annex and were adapted to the CBA requirements for each of the value chains and developed specifically with these specific value chains in mind. The decision to create these separate guiding documents in Word, rather than sharing the Excel template directly with stakeholders, was taken to make it as easy as possible for stakeholders to fill in their responses. The guiding documents were created by CU in close collaboration with WECR, who provided insights into the specific data requirements of each CBA. To enable the participation of key industry stakeholders from relevant markets, the guiding documents were created in English and translated to several languages, including German, Portuguese, Swedish, and Polish. These guiding documents serve as examples and can be adapted and tailored to other value chains belonging to different sectors as needed beyond this project. Please refer to Annex for copies of the guiding documents in English for the example of the wood value chain.

2. Creation of the data collection template

The data collection template is provided as an Excel file titled *D4.3_Data collection template for cost benefit analysis*, which can be utilised for data collection for a CBA. The data collection template was created as a result of multiple iterations rounds with CU, WEcR, other project partners, as well as CU scheme experts, in order to ensure that the template addresses the identified data needs and would be fit for use for performing the actual CBA calculations in Task 4.5. The template includes a comprehensive set of cost and benefit items, as well as environmental, social and economic externalities guided by the work conducted in Task 4.1. The indicators, especially direct and indirect costs, have been discussed with representatives from the two sister projects Harmonitor and STAR4BBS in joint meetings related to CBA calculations.

The 'Cover' tab of the Excel file works as a guide intended to help users to navigate to the relevant section of the Excel file (please see screenshot of this 'Cover page' below).

SUSTCERT4BIOBASED Project

Deliverable D4.3 Data collection template for cost benefit analysis

This Excel file is the output of Task 4.3 of the SUSTCERT4BIOBASED project. It contains a data collection template for conducting a Cost Benefit Analysis.

[The first tab provides the Cost Benefit Analysis \(CBA\) template](#)

[The second tab provides an overview of direct and indirect costs and benefits](#)

[The third tab includes the comprehensive list of indicators](#)

[The last tab can be used to note down company-specific information](#)

For further details on the template and the data collection process, please refer to the accompanying Reading Guide.

Figure 1: Excerpt from the Excel document: Cover tab

The first tab provides the data collection template itself, called the 'CBA template'. The table below (Table 1) summarises the categories and items, as well as the related units included in this CBA template. Please note that this table was developed based on the testing of the selected biobased value chains in this project and the available data and information on them. This Table 1 can be expanded by including more indicators from the comprehensive indicators list (Table 3) upon their availability for the specific biobased value chain certification under consideration. There are also columns available in the template to provide additional information on the data entry and to provide the source.

Table 1: Categories of the CBA template

Category	Item	Unit (per unit of product)	Non-certified product	Certified product
Direct costs	Auditing costs	Euro	n.a.	
	Certification fee	Euro	n.a.	
	Indirect costs related to sustainability compliance	Euro	n.a.	
Internal benefits related to certification	Price premium	Euro	n.a.	
	Efficiency improvements	Euro	n.a.	
	Improved market position	Euro	n.a.	
Environmental externalities	Climate change	kg CO ₂ -eq to air		
	Terrestrial acidification	kg SO ₂ -eq to air		
	Water use	m ³ water-eq consumed		
	Freshwater eutrophication	kg P-eq to freshwater		
	Land use	m ² a crop-eq		
	Fossil resource scarcity	kg oil-eq		
	Mineral resource scarcity	kg Cu-eq		
Social externalities	Living wage gap	Euro/year		
	Forced labour	Hours of involuntary working time/year		
	Child labour	Hours/year		
	Workplace injuries and death	Hours of lost working time/year		

In the second tab called ‘Overview of CBA items’ a descriptive table of direct and indirect costs and benefits, along with a description of each item, is included (see Table 2 below). Further information on the CBA methodology that led to the development of this overview can be found in Deliverable D4.1.

Table 2: Overview of direct and indirect cost and benefits

Category	Internal/external	Direct/Indirect	Item	Description
Costs	Internal	Direct	Auditing costs	Costs that a company has to pay for an external audit to become or remain certified
			Certification fees	Membership fee and/or quantity-dependent fee
		Indirect	Administrative indirect costs	Costs incurred when adapting the company or farm administration to adequate traceability tools and systems and man-days to ensure the correct (and documented) implementation of the chain of custody
			Indirect costs related to sustainability compliance, including training	Investments for adapting production and trade processes to the requirements of sustainability standards, training of workers in sustainable agriculture technologies and processes, etc.
	External	n.a.	Environmental	Environmental external costs (e.g., from pollution) arising from the production or consumption of a good or service
		n.a.	Social	Social external costs arising from the production or consumption of a good or service (e.g. child labour)

Benefits	Internal	Direct	Efficiency and/or management improvements within company	Benefits related to reduction in the use of inputs, such as water, fertilizers and energy
		Direct	Price premium	Additional revenues obtained by selling the certified product
		Indirect	Improved market position	Additional revenues obtained through image and branding, and meeting demands of the market
	External	n.a.	Environmental	Environmental external benefits arising from producing and/or consuming the certified product
		n.a.	Social	Social external benefits arising from producing and/or consuming the certified good or product

The third tab is the “Comprehensive Indicators list”. It contains the comprehensive list of indicators, detailing the environmental and social externalities that need to be internalized. The development of the data collection template began with the creation of this table providing a comprehensive overview of relevant environmental and social indicators. These indicators were based on sustainability criteria and principles, specifically focusing on environmental and social aspects identified from sustainability standards and certification schemes which were collated in WP 1 (Deliverable D1.2). Table 3 provides this comprehensive indicators list. The indicators for the environmental externalities are based on the impact categories of ReCiPe 2016 method [1]. The ReCiPe is a well-known impact assessment method for life cycle assessment, which converts emissions and resource extractions into a limited number of impact categories [1]. The midpoint level indicators of ReCiPe provides a coverage of a wide range of environmental impacts. The social indicators in Table 3 are selected based on the Social Hotspots Database [2]. To the best of our knowledge, this is the most extensive database that provides insight into social hotspots in product supply chains. The database covers 140 countries and regions and 57 economic sectors, and is used for social life cycle assessments [2]. This list of indicators was then narrowed down to ensure that those indicators that could be quantified in CBA are included for further analysis in the case studies.

Table 3: Comprehensive indicators list

Sustainability principles and criteria	Indicator	Unit (per unit of product)
Environmental Costs		
<u>Climate change</u>		
Reduce GHG emissions	Global warming potential	kg CO ₂ -eq to air
<u>Water use</u>		
Sustainable use of water	Water use	m ³ water-eq consumed
<u>Water quality</u>		
Maintaining and enhancing water quality	Freshwater eutrophication	kg P-eq to freshwater
	Freshwater ecotoxicity	kg 1,4-DCB-eq to freshwater
	Marine ecotoxicity	kg 1,4-DCB-eq to marine water
<u>Soil quality</u>		
Maintaining and enhancing soil quality and productivity	Terrestrial ecotoxicity	kg 1,4-DCB-eq to industrial soil
<u>Air quality</u>		
Restrict air pollution, promote good air quality	Ozone depletion	kg CFC-11-eq to air
	Ionising radiation	kBq Co-60-eq to air
	Fine particulate matter formation	kg PM2.5-eq to air

	Photochemical oxidant formation: terrestrial ecosystems	kg NO _x -eq to air
	Photochemical oxidant formation: human health	kg NO _x -eq to air
	Terrestrial acidification	kg SO ₂ -eq to air
	Human toxicity: cancer effects	kg 1,4-DCB-eq to urban air
	Human toxicity: non-cancer effects	kg 1,4-DCB-eq to urban air
<u>Land use and land transformation</u>		
Promote sustainable land use	Land use	m ² a crop-eq
<u>Depletion of resources</u>		
Promote efficient use of resources	Mineral resource scarcity	kg Cu-eq
	Fossil resource scarcity	kg oil-eq
Social Costs		
<u>Labour rights and working conditions</u>		
The differences between income of workers and local minimum wage/benchmarks	Living wage gap	Euro/year
Extra hours worked	Forced labour	Hours of involuntary working time/year
Work that involves child labour above allowed hours	Child labour	Hours/year
Occupational health and safety (workplace injuries)	Workplace injuries and death	Hours of lost working time/year
(Leave) hours used for education, child, adult or health	Other type of leave	Hours/year
<u>Equal opportunities</u>		
Difference in average earnings between men and women	Gender wage gap	Euro/year
Work hours related to discrimination in the workplace	Discrimination at workplace	Hours/year
Percentage of jobs held by immigrants	Immigrants as percentage of the population	%
Percentage of the population covered by social assistance programs	Social assistance programs	%
<u>Community and cultural impact</u>		
Percent of population that is indigenous	Indigenous group population	%
Number of laws to protect indigenous group according to International Labour Organization (ILO)	Protection of indigenous group	Number of laws
The potential for social unrest, protests, or conflict arising from resource competition, environmental degradation, or unequal distribution of benefits.	Risk of high social conflict	Hours of lost working time/year

Finally, the last tab in the Excel file includes a tab called 'General company information', which can be useful for recording general information which is company-specific. This includes company data, such as the name and address of the company, as well as the addresses of the site(s) considered for the assessment. It also includes a section for filling in the contact information of the company representative. Here it is noted that any personal data will be treated with confidentiality and not included in any reports. The date of the assessment can also be noted down, as well as any existing certifications that the company might have.

3. Testing on selected biobased value chains

3.1 Selection of certification schemes and value chains

Based on the work conducted in Task 4.2, three biobased value chains were defined. Please refer to deliverable D4.2 (*Selection of biobased value chains for cost benefit analysis*) for a more detailed description of how the value chains were selected. Relevant certification schemes were also identified and used as a basis for further developing the Excel template to address the differences between each value chain.

CU and WEcR selected the **chemical sector**, specifically the **ethanol from sugarcane** as the first value chain to focus on. For this first value chain, a leading certification scheme in the sugarcane value chain was selected as the applicable certification scheme. Since a significant share of the sugarcane production takes place in Brazil, CU integrated feedback from auditors and scheme experts from Control Union Brazil to ensure the practical applicability of the data collection template.

The second selected value chain concerns the production of **cotton** which was found to be representative of the **textile sector**. To assess this value chain, the focus was placed specifically on companies certified by Textile Exchange, specifically the Global Recycled Standard (GRS). Here, scheme experts and CU auditors from Germany were consulted and included in the data collection process. Due to data availability constraints, the scope for the textile sector was later adapted to also include Better Cotton certification. In this case, secondary data from literature was used in combination with targeted expert estimations (i.e. experts from CU auditors from India).

The third and final value chain refers to the **wood** value chain belonging to the **construction sector**, **and within this sector we focus specifically to** Forest Stewardship Council (FSC) certified wood value chain. For this sector, CU scheme experts and auditors from Germany, Poland, and Sweden were included in the data collection process, since these countries were identified as key markets for companies with FSC certification.

3.2 Creation of guiding documents

In order to facilitate the data collection process, three guiding documents were created and adapted to the specifics of each value chain. The guiding documents were structured as questionnaires, with certification-related questions and open fields for respondents, i.e., representatives of certified companies, to provide their responses. Depending on the data needs for each of the value chains, each guiding document is three to five pages long and corresponds to a specific certification scheme applicable to one of the three selected biobased value chains. The guiding documents were kept as short as possible in order not to discourage stakeholders from taking part and providing their data. In Annex 1 the questionnaire prepared for the wood value chain in English is provided as an example.

3.2.1 Chemical sector

For the chemicals sector, the guiding document focuses on the economic, environmental, and social factors associated with a leading certification in the sugarcane sector. It should be noted that, due to the sensitive nature of the data, no consent has been obtained yet from the certification scheme, hence the name of the certification scheme will be anonymised.

In addition to English, this guiding document was translated to Portuguese. This is because a major share of the sugarcane used as raw material for the bio-polyethylene used in this type of biobased

packaging comes from Brazil. As such, numerous companies and auditors involved in the data collection process are based in Brazil.

3.2.2 Textile sector

The guiding document for the textile sector focuses on the Textile Exchange Global Recycled Standard (GRS). Since both German and international GRS-certified textile companies were approached with an invitation to provide data, the guiding document for the textile sector was made available in both English and German to maximize its accessibility.

3.2.3 Construction sector

For the construction sector where a wood value chain is considered, a guiding document for Forest Stewardship Council (FSC) certification was created. Since key companies were identified and approached in Germany, Sweden, and Poland, the guiding document for the wood value chain was translated into German, Polish and Swedish.

3.3 Data collection process

3.3.1 Mapping value chains under consideration

For each of the sectors, the selected value chain was first mapped and validated by CU scheme experts. The goal of this was to ensure that companies from all relevant steps of the value chain would be contacted in the data collection process.

For the first value chain, the focus was on packaging made of biobased polyethylene, which can be derived from ethanol made of sugarcane. Figure 2 below illustrates the production process.

PRODUCTION OF ETHANOL FROM SUGARCANE

Typical value chain

Figure 2: Overview of the production process of ethanol produced from sugarcane

For cotton and wood, the value chains were similarly mapped, and can be seen in Figures 3 and 4, respectively.

(VIRGIN) COTTON GARMENT

Typical value chain

Figure 3: Example of a cotton value chain

WOOD PRODUCT

Typical value chain

Figure 4: Example of a wood value chain

3.3.2 Contacting stakeholders for data collection

After identifying the relevant actors across all three value chains, a multi-step stakeholder engagement process was conducted in order to raise companies' interest in participating in the project through providing data. This included contacting first trusted CU scheme experts and auditors from the relevant markets in order to identify relevant companies for the respective markets. After establishing contact through the CU experts, CU Germany contacted companies to invite them to participate in the project and provide their input either with an initial informative email, via a direct meeting with the company to inform them about the project and the advantages of participation. Follow-up exchanges with CU project partners ensured that participation was top-of-mind for relevant companies. Short information sheets were also provided and customised for each value chain. These informative documents provided an introduction to the SUSTCERT4BIOBASED project, a description of the CBA research, as well as an invitation for companies to participate in the research. Annex 2 provides an example of such an information sheet, which was targeted at a company within the wood value chain.

The companies were also invited to join online meetings, which were customised to the needs of each company. These meetings included a tailored PowerPoint presentation, and consisted of interactive, circa one-hour sessions where the company representatives could ask questions and better understand the benefits of participating. Finally, companies that had already agreed to take part in the research were asked to contact their suppliers who might be interested in participating and providing data, in order to expand the reach of the stakeholder engagement. In Annex 2, also an anonymised PowerPoint presentation used to inform companies about the project and the opportunity to join and provide feedback is included.

Following up with key company representatives via emails and calls throughout ensured that the data collection templates were filled in correctly and that the companies had the chance to ask questions and clarifications at any stage of the process.

In addition to targeting companies directly, an open online consultation was launched in order to attract further companies and offer more companies the opportunity to provide their feedback (see Figure 5). This open call was developed for companies involved in the selected three biobased sectors and launched in a joint effort between CU and communication partner WHITE. This involved creating and posting a brief project description geared towards biobased companies on the project's social media accounts, as well as creating an online form that enabled representatives of companies to express their interest in the project and share their contact details. The open call was executed with the intention of utilizing all available opportunities to establish contact with relevant companies involved in the selected biobased sectors that would be interested in participating in the data collection process.

Figure 5: Open call on LinkedIn

For the sugarcane to ethanol value chain, Brazil was identified as a key market for sugarcane as the raw material. As such, CU experts in Brazil reached out to multiple ethanol and bioplastics producers and invited them to participate in the project. After multiple rounds of meetings with companies, company-specific data for this value chain could be obtained from a leading company in the chemical sector. The company produces bio-based plastics from ethanol derived from sugarcane. Another company initially interested in participating in the project, declined to provide data on account of data sensitivity concerns. In order to avoid data gaps, data was also collected based on the requirements of the certification scheme, and calculations were made based on anonymised data from companies.

The data collection for the other two value chains is still ongoing. For the cotton value chain, with the support of CU Germany, over 200 GRS-certified companies were contacted and information was shared about the opportunity to participate in the project. As a result, three textile companies so far provided data for WP4. These three textile companies include a trader or GRS certified goods, a yarn producer, as well as a producer of textile garments from Germany. However, due to company size, lack of data collection internally within the companies, or choosing not to answer to certain parts of the questionnaire due to concerns of sensitive data, the responses obtained from these three companies were not sufficient for conducting a complete CBA. For this reason, the scope was expanded to include Better Cotton, and a desk research and targeted expert consultations with textile experts from CU India were conducted. For the wood value chain, through collaboration with CU experts in Germany, Poland, and Sweden, FSC-certified companies in these three countries were identified as potential candidates for data collection. As a result, one company so far has provided data for the wood value chain. The company in question processes forest raw material into renewable products, and is based in Sweden. Due to the limited input from companies directly, other data collection methods were also utilised, as described in Chapter 4 of this document.

4. Limitations

Throughout the process of creating the data collection template and the accompanying guiding documents, some limitations were identified. These mostly related to gaps in data collection, which was already identified as a potential risk for the CBA work in the early stages of the project.

Companies taking part in the data collection for WP4 were informed that participation in the research is voluntary, and they could drop out at any stage. A number of the participating companies opted out of answering some of the questions due to concerns of data sensitivity. The sensitive nature of the data required for CBAs, such as sensitive financial data, will likely remain an issue for CBA calculations in the future. For the purposes of this project, various approaches were adopted in order to minimise companies' concerns with regards to sensitive data; they were offered the option to only provide data that they were comfortable with sharing, and data anonymity and the fact that all results would be eventually aggregated was emphasised to companies.

Further concerns from stakeholders related to issues such as lack of resources or limited time. This was addressed by offering companies multiple ways to provide feedback: for example, through combining data collection with upcoming audits to ensure the time spent was as short as possible, and through offering the option to either provide data verbally in an in-person or online interview, or in a written form. Finally, the questionnaires presented in Annex 1 were created as an effort to make data provision in a written form as simple as possible. Here, the questionnaires were customised to each value chain and kept as short as possible, while also ensuring that the minimum requirements for the CBA would be met.

Finally, some of the companies reported simply not gathering the data required for such an analysis. Here, reasons listed included the small size of the company, limited access to data, and limited personnel resources. In such cases, the company was nevertheless presented the option to provide any input possible.

Despite all efforts to minimise risks linked to obtaining data, above difficulties resulted in some data gaps. For the purposes of this project and the remaining tasks in WP4, the issue of missing data was addressed by complementing the data collection with literature reviews and conducting desk research to make up for missing data. CU scheme experts and auditors from e.g., Germany, Brazil, and Poland have also been consulted to address some of the data gaps.

The focus of the work package was also adapted in an ongoing manner to ensure that results could be gleaned despite the data gaps. Especially for the textile sector, the considerable number of companies choosing to not provide sensitive or otherwise unavailable data led to data gaps. For this reason, the CBA conducted in Task 4.5 will look into the Better Cotton (BC) certification instead of GRS, since the literature research provided more extensive results for the BC certification scheme. This secondary data could be used to fill in the CBA-related data for the textile sector. Where applicable, CU experts from India were also consulted to address some of the gaps with regards to direct costs.

5. Conclusions and Recommendations

This deliverable aimed to develop a data gathering template to facilitate collection of data on biobased value chains for carrying out cost benefit analysis (CBA) of adoption of sustainability certification schemes and labels. For this purpose, a comprehensive list of indicators was created, but it was narrowed down to include only measurable indicators, which has been further narrowed into an illustrative example (CBA template). This broader list can be used to expand the CBA template by incorporating additional indicators into the calculations as they become available.

Conducting a CBA including internalisation of externalities is a complex and ambitious task. The issue of data sensitivity and difficulties with obtaining data were already predicted in the proposal phase of the SUSTCERT4BIOBASED project. Indeed, obtaining robust data from companies proved a challenging and time-consuming task. This can be attributed to the sensitive nature of the data, including reluctance to share information related to economical costs and benefits. Other issues identified include resource or personnel limitations, or simply companies not collecting this type of data in the first place.

Nevertheless, further research into conducting CBAs, including internalisation of externalities, is needed in the future in order to assess the feasibility of adopting certification. However, as it is foreseeable that companies will likely be hesitant to provide sensitive data, the data collection issues described in section 4 of this deliverable will likely prevail. It is recommended to consider these limitations when conducting research on this topic in the future. Ensuring anonymity and trust, and utilising further data collection opportunities through e.g., including certification schemes or utilising desk research are some of the options available for tackling the issue.

The various ways in which the data availability and data gap issues have been addressed have been described in this deliverable. These data collection issues could partially be addressed by using alternative sources of data, e.g., using certification costs available on scheme websites, or estimating auditing costs based on input from CU experts. However, the calculation of indirect costs remains difficult without direct data from companies.

The data collection approach detailed in this deliverable serves as a guide for conducting a CBA. However, it should be noted that despite the effort made to address the data gaps, many assumptions in relation to the data used will have to be made in the CBA. As such, the resulting CBA should always be interpreted with the data limitations and assumptions in mind.

The templates and accompanying guiding documents provided in this reading guide can be adapted to match the requirements of each upcoming CBA calculation. They serve as a solid starting point for conducting CBAs for other value chains, also beyond the SUSTCERT4BIOBASED project.

References

1. Huijbregts, M. A., Steinmann, Z. J., Elshout, P. M., Stam, G., Verones, F., Vieira, M. D., ... & van Zelm, R. (2016). ReCiPe 2016: a harmonized life cycle impact assessment method at midpoint and endpoint level report I: characterization. <https://rivm.openrepository.com/bitstream/handle/10029/620793/2016-0104.pdf?sequence=3&isAllowed=y>
2. Simapro, Social Hotspots Database. <https://simapro.com/products/social-hotspots-database/>

Annex 1 – Data Collection Questionnaire

(Example from the wood value chain)

Questionnaire Related to the Forest Stewardship Council (FSC) Certification

Thank you for agreeing to respond to this questionnaire. If you would like to have your company's name appear in project materials, such as publicly available reports, please indicate so below:

I consent to my company's name being included in e.g. public reports: Yes No

Company name (please fill in only if you would want it to be included): [Click or tap here to enter text.](#)

Kindly respond to the following questions and statements about FSC certification to the best of your ability. Additionally, you are welcome to provide a brief explanation or clarification for your responses when applicable.

Business Operations

Question	Answer	Explanation
What is your company's main business activity? If applicable, you are welcome to select multiple answers.	<input type="checkbox"/> Forest management	[optional: provide explanation or clarification here]
	<input type="checkbox"/> Timber harvesting	
	<input type="checkbox"/> Wood processing and manufacturing	
	<input type="checkbox"/> Trading and distribution	
	<input type="checkbox"/> Print and publishing	
What is the scale of your operations?	<input type="checkbox"/> Production of furniture and home goods	[optional: provide explanation or clarification here]
	<input type="checkbox"/> Other: [please specify here]	
	<input type="checkbox"/> Local	
	<input type="checkbox"/> National	
	<input type="checkbox"/> Europe	
Where do your primary sources of FSC-certified products come from?	<input type="checkbox"/> Global	[optional: provide explanation or clarification here]
	<input type="checkbox"/> Other: [please specify here]	
	<input type="checkbox"/> FSC-certified forests or plantations	
	<input type="checkbox"/> FSC-certified processing and manufacturing companies	
	<input type="checkbox"/> FSC-certified products from companies	

Other: [please specify here]

Business activities in relation to FSC certification

Product types with FSC Certification

[enter product type(s) here]

What percentages of your products are FSC certified (%)?

[enter value here]

What climatic zone do your FSC-certified products come from? If applicable, you are welcome to select multiple answers.

- Tropical climatic zone
- Subtropical climatic zone
- Temperate climatic zone
- Boreal climatic zone
- Mediterranean climatic zone
- Montane climatic zone
- Other: [please specify here]

What forest type do your FSC-certified products come from? If applicable, you are welcome to select multiple answers.

- Boreal forest
- Temperate forest
- Tropical rainforest
- Tropical dry forest
- Mangrove rainforest
- Plantation forest
- Other: [please specify here]

Please fill in the table below for only products with FSC certification

Item	Value	Unit
Annual production volume of FSC-certified products at your company	[enter value here]	Ton Other: [specify here]
Percentage of your total product line that is FSC-certified	[enter value here]	%

Total number of full-time employees working at the company [enter value here] Full-time equivalent

Year (on which information above is based)

Adoption of FSC certification

Questions	Answers	Explanation
a. The main motivation for being FSC certified is (select up to three answers):	<input type="checkbox"/> Our commitment to sustainability <input type="checkbox"/> Because our clients demand it <input type="checkbox"/> Because regulators demand it <input type="checkbox"/> To improve production efficiency <input type="checkbox"/> To improve management practices <input type="checkbox"/> To improve our market position <input type="checkbox"/> To get access to new market(s) <input type="checkbox"/> To strengthen our brand image <input type="checkbox"/> Other: [specify here]	[optional: provide explanation for selected answers]
b. The estimated increase in sales facilitated by FSC certification is:	<input type="checkbox"/> 0-5% <input type="checkbox"/> 6-10% <input type="checkbox"/> 11-15% <input type="checkbox"/> More than 16% <input type="checkbox"/> None	[optional: provide explanation or clarification here]
c. Being FSC certified enables me to negotiate a higher selling price for my products for different markets:	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No If yes, which? <input type="checkbox"/> Europe <input type="checkbox"/> North America <input type="checkbox"/> Asia <input type="checkbox"/> Other: [specify here]	If yes, by how much compared to before FSC certification? Europe XX% North America XX% Asia XX%

- Other: XX%
[specify]
- d. What is the largest market for your company's main FSC-certified product?
- Europe
 - North America
 - Asia
 - Other: [specify]
- [optional: provide explanation or clarification here]
- e. Getting FSC results in a change of the cost price
- The cost price increases
 - The cost price does not change
 - The cost price decreases
- If change, how much?
- 0-5%
 - 6-10%
 - 11-15%
 - More than 16%
 - Other: [specify here]
- f. Our company received subsidies from NGOs or the government to pursue FSC certification
- Yes
 - No
 - I don't want to say
- [optional: provide explanation for selected answers]

FSC certification costs

Item	Description	Value	Unit
Auditing costs	Audit fees	[enter value here]	Euros Other: [specify here]
Certification costs	Costs for the certification process, including application fees and membership fee	[enter value here]	Euros Other: [specify here]
Administration costs	Administrative costs incurred in adapting the company's process to align with FSC requirements	[enter value here]	Euros Other: [specify here]
Costs related to compliance with FSC requirements	Extra costs related to training staff members to work with FSC requirements along the supply chain	[enter value here]	Euros Other: [specify here]
	Investment in equipment required for complying with the FSC requirements	[enter value here]	Euros Other: [specify here]
	Consultancy service cost to get certificates	[enter value here]	Euros Other: [specify here]

Costs associated with ensuring fair labor practices and safe working conditions across the supply chain	[enter value here]	Euros Other: [specify here]
Costs associated with energy and water use for recycling processes	[enter value here]	Euros Other: [specify here]
Operational costs related to managing the environmental impact of the recycling processes (e.g., emissions control, waste management)	[enter value here]	Euros Other: [specify here]

Would you like to provide more information related to the social and environmental factors associated with being FSC certified? If so, kindly scroll to the next page and fill out the subsequent tables to the best of your ability. If you are unsure of the answer to any of the fields in the table, feel free to skip them. Any information you would be able to provide in the following tables would be much appreciated. Your contributions to the following tables will ultimately enable this project to better understand the environmental and social benefits of FSC certification, thereby providing valuable insights on sustainability certification schemes and labels for the entire wood industry!

Questions Related to Environmental and Social Benefits

Environmental Benefits

1. Do you collect environmental information for your company’s contribution to environmental sustainability? If yes, please fill in the table below and you may fill in more than the listed indicators.

Environmental Indicator	Value	Unit	Explanation (if applicable)
Sustainable harvesting	[enter here]	[enter here]	[enter here]
Protection of high conservation value areas	[enter here]	[enter here]	[enter here]
Species protection	[enter here]	[enter here]	[enter here]
Habitat preservation	[enter here]	[enter here]	[enter here]
[enter here]	[enter here]	[enter here]	[enter here]
[enter here]	[enter here]	[enter here]	[enter here]

2. What was the environmental performance of your company at the time of **the initial audit**? Kindly provide information that you have access to in the fields below. (Please provide your answer under the last column if your functional unit used to quantify these impacts is not per tonne).

Indicator	Value	Unit	Explanation (if applicable)
Greenhouse gas emissions	[enter here]	Kg CO ₂ eq./tonne	[enter here]
Water use	[enter here]	m ³ water/tonne	[enter here]
	[enter here]	Electricity: kWh/tonne	[enter here]
Fossil energy use	[enter here]	Natural gas: m ³ /tonne	[enter here]
	[enter here]	Diesel: L/tonne ...	[enter here]
[enter here]	[enter here]	[enter here]	[enter here]
[enter here]	[enter here]	[enter here]	[enter here]

3. What was the environmental performance of your company **5 years after the initial audit**? If the company was certified less than 5 years ago, refer to the most recent year for which data is available. (Please provide your answer under the last column if your functional unit used to quantify these impacts is not per tonne).

Indicator	Value	Unit	Explanation (if applicable)
Greenhouse gas emissions	[enter here]	Kg CO ₂ eq./tonne	[enter here]
Water use	[enter here]	m ³ water/tonne	[enter here]
	[enter here]	Electricity: kWh/tonne	[enter here]
Fossil energy use	[enter here]	Natural gas: m ³ /tonne	[enter here]
	[enter here]	Diesel: L/tonne	[enter here]

Social Benefits

4. Do you collect indicators related to the social information of your company's contribution to social sustainability? If yes, please fill in the table below and you may fill in more than the listed indicators.

Social Indicator	Unit	Value	Explanation (if applicable)
Community and indigenous rights protection	[enter here]	[enter here]	[enter here]
Fair wage for labors	[enter here]	[enter here]	[enter here]
[enter here]	[enter here]	[enter here]	[enter here]
[enter here]	[enter here]	[enter here]	[enter here]
[enter here]	[enter here]	[enter here]	[enter here]

5. What was the social performance of your company **at the time of the initial audit** and **5 years after the initial audit**? If the company was certified less than 5 years ago, refer to the most recent year for which data is available. Please fill out the information below:

	At the initial audit	5 years after audit	Explanation
Living wage gap (living wage minus current wage)	[enter here] \$/hour	[enter here] \$/hour	[enter here]
Work-related injury rate	[enter here] incidence/hours worked	[enter here] incidence/hours worked	[enter here]
Child labor used	[enter here] hours/year	[enter here] hours/year	[enter here]
Involuntary work	[enter here] hours/year	[enter here] hours/year	[enter here]

Many thanks for your replies!

We will treat all responses with full confidentiality and aggregate all data so nothing can be traced back to individual companies.

Annex 2 – Information shared with stakeholders (Example from the wood value chain)

Information sheet about opportunity to participate in the case study

Opportunity to gain insight and contribute to the latest developments in the field of sustainability certifications

Dear sir or madam,

Control Union is currently involved in [SUSTCERT4BIOBASED](#), a 3-year EU-funded research project assessing and promoting the adoption of sustainability certification schemes and labels for industrial biobased systems. The project aims to support tracing the sustainability of the products along European and international value chains across various biobased industries.

Together with two other research projects, SUSTCERT4BIOBASED is a project aiming to create a monitoring system for sustainability certification schemes and labels, which shall be adopted across European biobased markets. Such a monitoring system could play a pivotal role in making sense of the currently scattered field of sustainability certifications and labels. As part of the project, we are conducting a cost-benefit assessment related to the adoption of sustainable certification schemes.

We are reaching out to your company, as we will soon be starting to conduct small case studies. Our focus will be on companies that are FSC-certified, or that are planning to obtain a certification in the near future. If you are an FSC-certified company or interested in getting the FSC-certification soon, your participation in this case study could provide great mutual benefits.

Taking part in the project through a case study would provide you with the unique opportunity to get insight into upcoming developments within this field, as well as to have an influence on the upcoming Monitoring System. Such a monitoring system has the potential to influence the policy framework in Europe, which is why input from key actors along biobased value chain is so important for us.

Any additional preparation for the case study is not required, and we will provide further background information as well as the required materials. We will ensure that the participation is as smooth as possible for you; we can look at either online or in-person options, depending on your preferences. The review visit can alternatively be organised in parallel with your next upcoming FSC audit.

Joining the review visit would of course come at no additional cost to you but would greatly benefit the project and at the same time give you first-hand insight into the latest developments in the sustainability certification field.

If you would like to hear more about the project or how you can participate, please do not hesitate to contact us under: [xxx](#)

We hope to hear from you soon!

P.S. If you are interested to hear more about the project and its latest development, please take a look at the short video below, or visit the project's official [website](#). We would also be happy to organize a virtual call to answer any questions you might have about your potential participation.

Example PowerPoint presentation used during targeted information sessions with potential companies

PARTNERS

The SUSTCERT4BIOBASED project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement no. 101059785

Introduction to the SustCert4Biobased-project

Pilot audits/ case studies

Introduction

- Control Union is involved in a European research project that contributes to the set-up of a **monitoring system** for sustainability certification schemes and labels
 - To be adopted across European **bio-based markets**
 - Such a monitoring system can function in recognising certification schemes for bio-based products, similar to how it is done in RED II for bioenergy.
 - **Sugarcane** is identified as a key commodity for the bio-based market
 - This is your chance to give input and help as do a reality check and to **influence the burden** this might have on companies like yours

Case studies

What's in it for you?

- Control Union will in early 2024 conduct case studies with companies with existing or upcoming certification
- Relevant companies will get the chance to test the practical feasibility of this monitoring system
 - Chance to have your say in the development of this system, and
 - Get first-hand insight into the upcoming developments within the fast-developing European bio-based market
 - Preparing for the future as the European bio-markets get increasingly relevant

Case studies

Practical aspects

- Companies will take part at no cost
- We will ensure that the time efforts related to taking part will be as limited as possible;
 - Participation can take place both online and offline, according to your wishes
 - Wherever possible, we will use existing data to keep the time spent to a minimum
 - **Note: when mutually agreed on, existing data from previous certification audits can be used where applicable to save time and avoid the duplication of work**

Examples of data needed from companies

- Environmental footprints: emissions, water usage, water waste, land use, chemical usage, pesticides, herbicides, other environmentally friendly initiatives across the supply chain.
- Safety and incidence: number of injuries and death, the safety standards, compensation policies.
- Employment information: number of employees, distribution of employees in term of gender, age, ethnicity. Wage information and the share of temporary contracts. Maternity and sick leave policies.
- Community engagement: is there a relationship between the firm and regional entities such as city council? Does the firm contribute to the social programs? If yes, how?

Interested in taking part?

- We hope you will join us in this project and help us shape the monitoring system to be easy to use and applicable in practice
- If you have any questions, please **get in touch** with the team:
 - (emails anonymised)
- We look forward to collaborating on this together!

Further engagement opportunities: Network of Interest

ARE YOU INTERESTED IN BIOECONOMY?
Join our Network of Interest

SUSTCERT4BIOBASED's Network engages a wide range of participants and supports the international networking and knowledge transfer

Role

- ✓ Connect with other individuals and organisations
- ✓ Publicize recent advancements and trends
- ✓ Share your knowledge and views on bioeconomy certification related aspects
- ✓ Participate in the bi-annual online meetings to discuss various issues from the sector and the project

Visit our website and Join the Network

www.sustcert4biobased.eu

Type of participants
Policy officers, label owners, standardization bodies, certification bodies, biomass producers, industrial operators, traders, local authorities, local organizations, unions, civil society etc.

Member of the European Union

- If you are interested in further collaboration with other companies, you are also more than welcome to join the project's „Network of Interest“
- The Network of Interest organises regular events and networking options for interested stakeholders
- To find out more and to sign up for the network, you can visit the project's [website](#)
- Participation in the Nol is fully voluntary, and you can of course take part in our pilot audits without joining the Nol
- On the next slide we present some further options for promoting your participation in the project, if you so wish

Further engagement opportunities: events and social media

- **Connect with other members:** Our bi-annual Nol meetings are the perfect opportunity to connect with other members of our network and share ideas.
- **Sharing your story:** We'd love to feature you in an interview on our website or social media channels! Share your experiences and insights with our audience.
- **Showcase your expertise:** As an article writer for our project's website, you'll have the opportunity to showcase your expertise on a variety of topics related to our project.
- **Share your expertise as a speaker:** Are you an expert in your field? Share your knowledge and insights with our community by speaking at one of our events.

Our Network of Interest Interview Series

The 'Your Corner' is a Senior Scientist for BioBased...
 With support from a sustainability assessment of...
 SUST CERT 4 BIOBASED Coordinator

INTERVIEW
 With
LOEK VERWIJST
 Managing Director Peterson Project GmbH

Voices from our Network
 Network of Interest Interview Series: Loek Verwijst

www.sustcert4biobased.eu

CONTACT US: info@sustcert4biobased.eu

About SUSTCERT4BIOBASED

SUSTCERT4BIOBASED is an EU funded (Horizon Europe) project aiming at defining and promoting the adoption of effective and robust sustainability certification schemes and business-to-business labels for industrial biobased systems to support tracing the sustainability (environmental, social, economic) of biobased products along the value chains and trades within the EU and globally for responsible production and consumption. This objective is realised by the development of a monitoring system, mapping of the current situation in global trade flows of biological resources and biobased products, and feasibility assessment from the adoption of certification schemes and labels considering actual economic as well as internalized environmental and social costs and benefits. The results of the project are leveraged to provide recommendations to four key target groups: policy makers, sustainability system community, industrial biobased value chain actors, and regional bioeconomy stakeholders. These ambitions are addressed by a strong, well-balanced and multi-disciplinary consortium comprised of 5 complementary partners. SUSTCERT4BIOBASED thereby supports the development of harmonized system requirements, continuous improvement of sustainability certification schemes and labels and contributes towards establishing a circular, climate-neutral and sustainable biobased industry.

PARTNERS

Stichting Wageningen Research (WR)
www.wur.nl

Fundacion Circe Centro de Investigacion de Recursos y Consumos Energeticos (CIRCE)
www.fcirce.es

White Research SRL (WHITE)
white-research.eu

Environmental Coalition on Standards (ECOS)
www.ecostandard.org

Control Union Certifications Germany GmbH (CU)
www.controlunion-germany.com

CONTACT US

info@sustcert4biobased.eu

- Sustcert4biobased
- @SUSTCERT4BIO
- SUSTCERT4BIOBASED
- SUSTCERT4BIOBASED

VISIT

www.sustcert4biobased.eu